

MODEL AGES OF LIGHT PLAINS AND CRATER FLOORS IN THE NORTHERN POLAR REGION, MOON. B. Giuri¹, C. H. van der Bogert² and M. S. Robinson¹. ¹Intuitive Machines, Phoenix, AZ, USA bgiuri@intuitivemachines.com, ²Institut für Planetologie, Universität Münster, Germany.

Introduction: The lunar axial tilt is hypothesized to have drifted over the past few billion years to its current value of 1.54° with respect to the ecliptic [1]. The current orientation means that impact crater floors in the polar regions do not receive direct sunlight, forming permanently shadowed regions (PSRs). Due to the frigid temperatures in these regions ($<110\text{K}$), PSRs can act as a volatile sink, with significant scientific implications for upcoming and future human exploration missions. The lunar southern polar region is currently the primary target of intense study and human exploration due to the potential presence of resources such as consumable volatiles [2-4]. However, PSRs are also present in the northern polar region, albeit smaller, fewer, and more isolated than their southern counterparts. In this study, we continue our examination of the model ages of light plains and smooth crater floors in the northern polar region to better constrain the origins of basin and crater ejecta and, if present, the source and ages of volatiles.

Data: Here, we used the Planetary Data System-released (PDS) LOLA Digital Elevation Model (LDEM) Hillshade map 60-90N at 120 m/pixel to (1) avoid the challenging lighting conditions in the PSRs and (2) select a uniform resolution suitable for crater counting measurements, given the lower data density of north polar products compared to the south pole [5]. The low-resolution dataset used here however calls for the acknowledgment of the uncertainty linked to (1) the ability to clearly identify and measure $\leq 1\text{km}$ diameter craters, (2) missing the crater diameter range at which a resurfacing event might have occurred, and (3) larger error bars on the model ages introduced by the larger pixel scale of the north polar database compared to the south polar data. We also used the latest global light plains map [6] to select suitable areas for crater size-frequency distribution measurements, while also avoiding large secondary chains and clusters [7, 8].

Methods: We conducted our investigation using QGIS. CSFD measurements were made using OpenCraterTool [9] and plotted using CraterStats [10] using the production function (PF) and chronology function (CF) of [11], and Poisson timing analysis [12] for absolute model age (AMA) determination.

Results: We identified ten areas of interest in the northern circum-polar region within light plain units [6]. Of these, eight areas are within the crater floors of Lovelace, Byrd, De Sitter U, Baillaud A, Merrill, Plaskett, Peary, and Baillaud craters, and two cover the northern highlands (LP1 and LP2; Table 1).

AMAs could be assigned to all areas except the Merrill crater floor materials, which we found to be in equilibrium. Our results hint at two model age groups (Fig. 1): several areas around the pole date to ≥ 3.9 Ga, with two areas nearest to the pole at just over 4 Ga old. Further work is required to assess whether these ages represent statistically similar or distinct events. Nevertheless, based on the current results, it is likely that most of the northern circum-polar region of the Moon was affected by the Imbrium event, assuming a 3.92 Ga formation age [13].

Area name	km ²	Crater diameter fit range	Geologic map unit	AMA (Ga)
1 - Lovelace	442	1.4km - 5km	Ic ₂ - Nt	$3.91^{+0.068}_{-0.084}$
2 - Byrd	1030	820m - 10km	lp - pNc	$4.01^{+0.013}_{-0.013}$
3 - DeSitterU	498	680m - 10km	lp - pNc	$3.91^{+0.018}_{-0.019}$
4 - BaillaudA	714	690m - 10km	lp - pNc	$3.90^{+0.016}_{-0.016}$
5 - LP1	10400	1.5km - 10km	lif	$3.94^{+0.015}_{-0.015}$
6 - LP2	635	700m - 10km	lp	$3.94^{+0.015}_{-0.016}$
7 - Merrill	-	-	lp - Nc	-
8 - Plaskett	1530	930m - 10km	Ic ₂	$4.00^{+0.014}_{-0.014}$
9 - Peary	1560	1.3km - 10km	lp - pNc	$4.06^{+0.020}_{-0.020}$
10 - Baillaud	1460	920m - 10km	lp - pNc	$3.91^{+0.018}_{-0.019}$

Table 1: Listed are the ten LP areas identified in this work with related information about area size in km², the crater diameter range fit to derive the AMAs, and the corresponding geologic units of [15].

Discussion and Conclusion: Although several lines of evidence from orbital observations and the LCROSS experiment both suggest and challenge the presence of water ice and other volatiles in PSRs (LEND, Diviner, LAMP, LOLA, M³, Radar, LROC NAC, and ShadowCam instruments), the volatile abundance and distribution remain uncertain for both poles. Regardless, distinguishing aspects of the lunar poles are (1) the fewer ice detections over the north pole compared to the south [16,17], and (2) the model ages of ejecta materials, both of which can provide critical background information for strategic planning and execution in human and sample return missions.

Radiance studies using ShadowCam and M3 ice signatures show no significant differences between the poles, except for the fewer detections in the northern polar region. This finding might be due to (a) the fewer, smaller PSRs, (b) if ice is present, small abundances may not be detected using orbital instruments, (c) the presence of buried ice, (d) the absence of ice entirely, or a combination of all of the above [16,17]. Nevertheless, most of the count areas investigated at this stage of our study are sunlit, thus the absence of volatile signatures is not unexpected. Expanding the study area to PSRs could provide further insights into the source and ages of potential volatiles.

From our previous study [18], we found that south polar PSRs and sunlit deposits yield model ages ranging from ~ 2.4 Ga to ~ 3.8 Ga, indicating their emplacement via multiple impact events. Here, we find a recurring ≥ 3.9 Ga age across all our areas (except Merrill; Table 1), thus establishing that the northern polar region smooth deposits are older than the southern smooth deposits and might be related to the formation of Imbrium basin.

References:

- [1] Siegler et al. (2016), *Nature* 531, 480-484. [2] Spudis & Lavoie (2010), *Space manufacturing conference 14*. [3] Gawronka A. J. et al. (2020), *Adv. in Space Res.*, vol. 66, I-6, pp 12471264. [4] Flahaut et al. (2019), *PSS* 180. [5] Barker M. K. et al. (2025), *Planet. Sci. J.* 6 83. [6] Giuri, B. et al. (2024), *PSJ Special issue*. [7] Neukum G. et al. (2001), *Space sci. Rev.* 96, 55-86. [8] Hiesinger H. et al. (2011), *The Geo. Society of America, Special Paper* 477. [9] Heyer T. et al. (2023), *PSS* 231. [10] Michael & Neukum (2010), *EPSL* 294, 223. [11] Neukum G. (1983), *Habilitation Dissertation for Faculty Membership, Ludwig-Maximilians-Univ.* [12] Michael G. G. et al. (2016), *I-277*, 279-285. [13] Nemkin et al. (2021), *Geochemistry* 81(1), 125683. [14] Giuri et al. (2025), *LPSC 2210*. [15] Fortezzo et al. (2020), Unified geologic map of the Moon. [16] Li et al. (2018), *PNAS* 115, 8907. [17] Ando et al. (2025), *PSJ* 6 62. [18] Giuri et al. (2025), *JGR:Planets* 129(11).

Figure 1: CSFD R-plot examples of LP2 - area 6 and Plaskett crater floor - area 8 with corresponding randomness analyses.